

SEALIVE

Strategies of circular **E**conomy and **A**vanced bio-based solutions
to keep our **L**ands and seas **a**l**I**VE from plastics contamination

Deliverable 7.1

List and details of current standards for biodegradation and ecotoxicity

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Summary

SEALIVE (Grant Agreement number 862910) is a Horizon2020-funded project that aims at changing the current business models and strategies starting from the development of new biopolymers from natural sources to new the production and validation of specific plastics solutions including their best practices of end of life. With the joint effort of 24 partners ranging from raw material providers, convertors, end users, recyclers, policy experts, certification organizations and NGOs, SEALIVE project strives to boost the usage of biomaterials in the circular economy.

The general objective of SEALIVE is to develop innovative business models for advanced bio-based plastics directly supporting the Plastics Strategy set by the EC. The project will implement sustainable solutions based on novel bio-based plastics to avoid plastics ending up on land and sea and support the ambition of biopolymer producers with cutting-edge processing technologies, to follow the best end-of-life channels and build up a strong reference framework for the policy makers and harmonisation. The solutions to be developed within the SEALIVE include new bio-based plastics materials, recycling-by-design techniques and cutting-edge compounding and extrusion technologies that reach market products requirements, as well as effective end-of-life solutions targeting circular economy. In order to guarantee the adoption of the innovations and strategies defined within SEALIVE, the newly developed solutions will be supported with policy, pre-normative, and training actions in several countries across Europe.

Improvement of current standards for biodegradation, composting and recycling is important to address the issues of eco-toxicity, safety and influence of plastic ageing on the environment. Such standards harmonise industry practices worldwide and facilitate market acceptance of final products, which makes them applicable across various groups of stakeholders. It is therefore necessary to get an overview of the global landscape of standardisation in the areas of biodegradation and ecotoxicity in order to take advantage of existing standardisation activities and to ensure a thorough understanding of the needs and requirements of the involved stakeholders.

The objective of the present document is to analyse the status of current standardisation in the relevant areas and to point towards actions that can increase its effectiveness, ensure inclusion of all relevant stakeholders and their interests and improve the sustainability of plastic management starting from the production of bio-based plastics through their recycling to their end-of-life solutions. Further objective of the document is to provide a baseline for subsequent analysis of the processes and regulations of the bio-based plastics life cycle that are not addressed by current standardisation activities.

The report is structured around the main scopes of application of standards in the areas of biodegradation and ecotoxicity, starting from test schemes, analysis and specifications of plastic compounds to the environmental aspects of recovery and recycling of plastic waste.

The report reviews relevant standards and outlines the scope of each in effort to help identify the gaps in the areas not properly addressed by ongoing standardisation activities. The gap analysis will be further addressed in the Subtask 7.1.5. Pre-normative research to fill the gaps, which will allow the consortium to focus on these gaps while setting up test programs and performing pre-normative research in different environments such as soil, water, or compost, related to biodegradation and environmental safety of plastics and products.

Contents

Summary	1
Contents	2
1. Objective	3
2. Background	3
3. Methodology.....	4
3.1. Abbreviations	5
4. Results & Discussion	6
4.1. CEN Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards	6
4.2. ISO Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards.....	7
4.3. ASTM Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards.....	8
4.4. Other relevant standardization initiatives	8
5. Conclusion.....	9
6. List of tables	10
7. Appendix	11

1. Objective

The main objective of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the standardization activities in the areas of biodegradation and ecotoxicity, which reflects the objective of the Subtask 7.1.1 *Current standards for biodegradation and ecotoxicity* within the Task 7.1 *Pre-normative studies for standards on biodegradation, environmental safety and organic recycling* to create an inventory of project-relevant existing standards and current standardization activities.

The second objective of this deliverable is to provide background information for future gap identification and analysis within the Subtask 7.1.5 *Pre-normative research* to fill the gaps and Task 7.2 *Comparison of current to real life standards on biodegradability*. The identified standards (published and those under development) will be mapped against the results of the first materials characterization (Tasks 2.1 *Synthesis and characterization of bio-based materials from different biomass sources*, 2.2 *Development of bio-based additives and fluorescent markers for plastics formulations* and 2.3 *Formulation and production of new bio-polymer plastics with advanced properties at pilot scale*), especially to identify gaps in biodegradation and ecotoxicity standards, and the potential addition of some photodegradation step into the standard procedures for the biodegradation testing.

This report together with the gap analysis will serve as a cornerstone for the New Work Item Proposals, to be delivered at the end of the project.

2. Background

40% of the 58 million tons of plastics produced in Europe are used in packaging, but only 40% of the packaging waste is recycled.

Addressing this issue, SEALIVE aims to cover the whole life cycle of the materials and items made of bio-based plastics. The project will gather the relevant data from strategically selected use cases and channel them to develop three main bio-based materials: PLA, PHA and starch originating from organic waste and micro-algae. Through its 8 demonstrators (rigid food containers, flexible packaging for deep-frozen and high-sea fishing applications, agricultural films, fish crates, fishing nets, aquaculture mesh bag and single use plastics) SEALIVE will ensure reduction of the pollution of soils and water media primarily by packaging plastic waste, but also by all other sorts of plastic landing in the sea and in the landfills. In addition, the project will also cover the whole value chain from the business models, management and standardization to policy making. The project will benefit from the integration of different actors of the value chains with the main aim to decrease the leakage of plastics on land and sea.

SEALIVE will promote the circular innovation by following the life cycle of the product from its creation until the end-of-life. Technologies developed within the SEALIVE project will ensure the recyclability by design, followed by the development of new sustainable solutions. The project will contribute to the development of EU-harmonised criteria for biodegradability and a sustainability framework that increase market transparency and improves waste management practices on land and sea.

SEALIVE, working in accordance with the EU Plastics Strategy, aims to ensure that circularity and sustainability can be implemented in the short term. The developed solutions will serve as a

background and applied tools to raise awareness and create a better framework for systemic innovations, as well as for uptake of results through broad stakeholder engagement.

SEALIVE promotes various types of collaboration strategies between all partners of the project along the whole value chain and beyond, including training activities. It brings together the representatives of the environmental sciences, industries and technology developers with the goal to enhance the results of the project and ensure its replicability. Training targeting key stakeholders will take place in each of the three demonstration sites for marine application. Certified training modules will be developed aiming to deliver the training to the key stakeholders with the focus on the opportunities that lie within the blue economy and the bioeconomy.

SEALIVE will foster the innovation and the usage of biomaterials, the reuse and recyclability of products (renting/leasing models for instance) and their biodegradability in both conditions (soil and marine). In addition, SEALIVE will contribute to the understanding of the technical, economic and social barriers associated to current bio-based application. A list of policy recommendations to support the development and the uptake of the new bio-based materials will be developed. SEALIVE will also foster the development and uptake of the innovative bio-based materials globally, including agricultural policies, R&D support policies, as well as trade and industry policies

The report developed primarily for the SEALIVE consortium members and publicly available for all interested parties identifies national and international standards, guidelines and regulations relevant to the biodegradation and ecotoxicity of plastic waste. This will help set a direction for future standardisation activities.

3. Methodology

Initial literature review on the topic of digital investigation was conducted by Austrian Standards International. It identified the broad areas of focus that were further classified according to their area of application (Plastic, Water quality, Packaging, Textiles, Bio-based products, Soil, Algae and several special case standards).

The content of this report is based on a combination of resources, derived from standards databases of The European Committee for Standardization (CEN), The International Organization for Standardization (ISO), The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), American Society for Testing and Materials International (ASTM), as well as contributions from the consortium partners.

The database search was performed using the following keywords: bio-based, biodegradation, ecological assessment, ecotoxicity, emission, packaging, plastic, recycling, sustainability, waste. All identified standards were checked for their relevance to the project.

3.1. Abbreviations

The following table represents an overview of abbreviations used in connections with standardisation.

Table 1. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AFNOR	Association française de normalisation
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
AWI	Approved new Work Item
CD	Committee draft
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CWA	CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreement; standardisation deliverable from a CEN and/or CENELEC workshop
EN	Standard adopted by CEN, CENELEC and/or ETSI
ESO	European Standardisation organisation; the ESO's are CEN, CENELEC and ETSI
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers / standards developed by IEEE
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation / standards developed by ISO
NSB	National Standardisation Body
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
PLA	Poly lactide
SC	Sub-committee allocated by a Technical committee
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
SPCR	SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden, Certification Rules
SR	Special report developed by ESO
TC	Technical committee
TR	Technical report developed by ESO
TS	Technical specification developed by ESO
UNI	National Standardization Body of Italy
WD	Working Draft developed by ESO
WG	Working Group to which work is allocated by a Technical committee based on an approved new work item and drafting standardisation deliverables
WP	Work Package

4. Results & Discussion

In total, 114 published standardization documents and standards in development related to biodegradation and ecotoxicity have been identified. The vast majority of them originates from CEN and ISO, further relevant documents are provided by ASTM and several European organisations and initiatives, including NSBs.

4.1. CEN Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards

54 relevant standards, published by several CEN TCs, were identified (*Table 2. CEN standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity*). The TCs covering the areas of biodegradability and ecotoxicity include:

- CEN/TC 249-Plastics

The scope of the TC covers standardization of terminology, test methods, specifications, classifications and designation systems, environmental aspects, joining systems and techniques, of plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products (thermoplastics, thermosets, degradable plastics, bio-based polymers, thermoplastic elastomers, composites, reinforcement products for plastics, recyclates).

20 relevant standards cover the areas of terminology, requirements to biodegradable films, testing (test schemes and specifications for compostability and disposability in waste water, methods of determination of biodegradation and disintegration), as well as general environmental aspects of plastic.

- CEN/TC 230-Water analysis

The scope of this TC covers standardization in the area of water analysis, including definition of terms, sampling of water, measurement and reporting.

12 relevant standards address primarily testing of biodegradability of organic compounds in aqueous medium, as well as guidance on assuring the quality of biological and ecological assessments in the aquatic environment.

- CEN/TC 261 Packaging

The scope of this TC covers standards dealing with terminology, dimensions, capacities, marking, test methods, performance requirements and environmental aspects in the field of packaging and unit loads.

Eight relevant standards address requirements for biodegradable packaging, testing (test schemes and methods for evaluation of biodegradation and disintegration of packaging), as well as criteria and methodologies for life cycle analysis of packaging.

- CEN/TC 411 Bio-based products

The scope of this TC covers the areas of biobased products including terminology, sampling, certification tools, bio-based content, application of and correlation towards life cycle analysis, sustainability criteria for biomass used and for final products, and aspects where further harmonization is needed on horizontal level. In addition, it covers bio-solvents including product functionality, biodegradability and, if necessary, product-specific aspects.

10 relevant standards address a wide spectrum of issues, related to bio-based products, including vocabulary, determination of the products' content, sustainability criteria, as well as guidelines for Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Inventory.

- CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices

The scope of this TC is standardization of methods for the environmental characterization of soil, solid and liquid waste, biowaste and sludge. This covers: Sampling, assessment methods and vocabulary; Digestion / extraction, chemical analysis, physical methods, quality assurance and quality control (laboratories); Where appropriate and decided by matrix specific environmental Technical Committees: leaching tests, screening methods, sample pre-treatment, biological and microbiological analysis, reporting.

EN ISO 11266:2020 (Draft) about the guidance on laboratory testing for biodegradation of organic chemicals in soil under aerobic conditions was identified.

- CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products

The scope of this TC covers specification, classification, terminology and determination methods for algae (genera) and algae-based products immediately derived from or used in algae production processes. In addition, guidance on the specific application of algae products as feedstock or intermediates for energy and non-energy products may be developed.

EN 17477:2020 (Draft) about the identification of the biomass of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes — Detection and identification with morphological and/or molecular methods was identified.

- CEN/TC 292 Characterization of waste

The scope of this now disbanded TS covers standardization of procedures to determine the characteristics of waste and waste behaviour, especially leaching properties and standardization of subsequent terminology. The only standard, conditionally relevant for the project, covers the process of preparation of waste samples for ecotoxicity tests.

- CEN/BT/WG 209 Biobased products (disbanded)

The Working Group, created in 2009 with the aim to produce an overview of already existing standards on all types of bio-based products, identify research needs and produce recommendations for a standardization work programme, was disbanded in 2010. The group produced an overview of research needs relevant to the development of standards for bio-based products (CEN/TR 16208).

4.2. ISO Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards

31 relevant standards, published by several ISO TCs, were identified ([Table 3. ISO standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity](#)). The TCs covering the areas of biodegradability and ecotoxicity include:

- ISO/TC 38 Textiles

The scope of this TC covers fibres, yarns, threads, cords, rope, cloth and other fabricated textile materials, the methods of test, terminology and definitions relating thereto, textile industry raw materials, auxiliaries and chemical products required for processing and testing, as well as specifications for textile products.

One standard, relevant for the project, was identified within this TC, dealing with the measurement of emission mass of fibre debris from textile products for microplastics detection.

- ISO/TC 61 Plastics, SC 14 Environmental aspects

The scope of this TC covers all standardization activities in the field of plastics relating to environmental and sustainability aspects, with the focus on biobased plastics, biodegradability, environmental footprint, resource efficiency, characterization of plastics leaked into the environment, waste management including organic, mechanical and chemical recycling.

27 relevant standards address test methods and requirements (ecotoxicity, biodegradation and disintegration testing, determination of bio-based content), assessment of biodegradation rate, characteristics biodegradable products (drinking straws, shopping bags), guidelines for the recovery and recycling of plastics waste, as well as characteristics of carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics.

- ISO/TC 122 Packaging, SC 4 Packaging and environment

The scope of this TC covers activities aimed to reduce the environmental impact of packaging and minimize the risk of technical barriers to trade.

One relevant standard has been identified, addressing procedures and requirements for packaging, suitable for organic recycling.

- ISO/TC 147 Water quality, SC 5 Biological methods

The scope of this TC covers biological aspects of water quality.

Two relevant standards were identified within this TC, addressing determination and evaluation of biodegradability in an aqueous medium.

4.3. ASTM Biodegradation and Ecotoxicity Standards

ASTM Committee D20 on Plastics comprises of 700 members, includes 23 technical subcommittees and has jurisdiction of over 475 standards. These standards regulate all aspects important to the effective utilization of plastics, including specimen preparation, material specifications and methodologies for mechanical, thermal, optical and analytical testing¹.

Within ASTM, 23 standardization documents were identified, among them 13 standards, 2 specifications and 8 Work Item Proposals that address various aspects of plastic biodegradation (summarized in the *Table 4. ASTM D20 standards on plastics biodegradation*). No standards concerning ecotoxicity have been identified.

4.4. Other relevant standardization initiatives

A number of relevant standardization initiatives originate from NSBs such as AFNOR and UNI, as well as from SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden and The Circular Plastics Alliance (summarized in the *Table 5. Other relevant standardization deliverables*). The latter represents an initiative encompassing over 230 stakeholders from industry, academia and public authorities along with private actors active in the plastics value chains in the European Union. The Alliance aims to increase the use of recycled plastics into new products with the ambitious target to reach at least 10 million

¹ <https://www.astm.org/COMMITTEE/D20.htm>

tons of recycled plastics being used for products and packaging in Europe each year by 2025². In September 2019, CEN and CENELEC signed the declaration of the Circular Plastic Alliance (CPA)³.

Most of the standardization initiatives mentioned in this subchapter address composting of plastics and polymeric waste for home and industry (requirements, test methods and specifications for the materials). The declaration of the Alliance adopts a broader approach and covers the following topics:

1. Design for recycling guidelines and their regular update to ensure uptake of innovations
2. Shifting to zero plastic waste to nature and zero landfilling of plastic waste
3. Development of a R&D agenda on circular plastics addressing the technological barriers to meet the market and regulatory needs
4. Mapping of the investments and funding needed for collection, sorting, recycling and converting of plastics
5. Development of a harmonised EU value chain voluntary system to monitor volumes of recycled plastics used in European products

5. Conclusion

Standardisation is a very important tool to ensure that the solutions developed during the project are accepted by the market and can be utilized in the new products and processes covering all the plastics value chain from the raw materials to end-of-life solutions. It is also of special importance to increase the market transparency and to improve the waste management practices on land and sea.

This deliverable within the WP7 Task 7.1 provides an overview of existing standards and the ongoing standardisation work in a wide area of relevance to the SEALIVE project. 114 standards were identified, among them – 54 European standards developed by CEN, 31 international standards developed by ISO and IEC, 23 standards developed by ASTM International and 6 standardization initiatives developed by several NSBs and The Circular Plastics Alliance. Of them, most of the standards refer to testing (test schemes and methods of determination) and specifications for compostability, biodegradability and disintegration of plastics.

This overview provides a baseline for the next deliverables within the WP7, the reports D7.2: *Pre-normative work on marine standardisation and anaerobic digestion*, D7.3: *Pre-normative research on identified gaps in standardisation*, as well as for the D7.5: *a series of New Work Item Proposals*. While the list of identified standards is not exhaustive, this report serves as a reference on the key standards in biodegradation and ecotoxicity for the consortium members as well as for any expert developing bio-based solutions to reduce contamination of the nature by plastics.

² https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/policy/circular-plastics-alliance_en

³ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news/articles/Pages/AR-2019-016.aspx>

6. List of tables

Table 1. Abbreviations	5
Table 2. CEN standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity	11
Table 3. ISO standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity	21
Table 4. ASTM D20 standards on plastics biodegradation	27
Table 5. Other relevant standardization deliverables	31

7. Appendix

Table 2. CEN standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity

Committee	Standard	Scope
1	CEN/TC 249 Plastics EN 14995:2006 Plastics - Evaluation of compostability - Test scheme and specifications	This European Standard specifies requirements and procedures to determine the compostability or anaerobic treatability of plastic materials.
2	EN 14987:2006 Plastics - Evaluation of disposability in wastewater treatment plants - Test scheme for final acceptance and specifications	This European Standard specifies test methods and criteria which are to be applied in order to verify if a solid plastic material can be considered as disposable in waste water treatment plants, i.e. it does not create problems for the environment and for the drainage systems.
3	CEN/TR 15351:2006 Plastics - Guide for vocabulary in the field of degradable and biodegradable polymers and plastic items	This guide provides the vocabulary to be used in the field of polymers and plastic materials and items.
4	EN 17228:2019 Plastics - Bio-based polymers, plastics, and plastics products - Terminology, characteristics and communication	This document specifies the vocabulary, methods for characterization, and templates for reporting about bio-based polymers, plastics, and plastics products (including semi-finished plastics products and composites).
5	EN 17033:2018 Plastics - Biodegradable mulch films for use in agriculture and horticulture - Requirements and test methods	This document specifies the requirements for biodegradable films, manufactured from thermoplastic materials, to be used for mulch applications in agriculture and horticulture. It also specifies the test methods to assess these requirements as well as requirements for the packaging, identification and marking of films.

Committee	Standard	Scope
6	EN 17417:2019 (Draft) Determination of the ultimate biodegradation of plastics materials in an aqueous system under anoxic (denitrifying) conditions - Method by measurement of pressure increase	This document specifies a method for the determination of the ultimate anoxic biodegradability of plastics made of organic compounds, where the amount of the produced nitrogen and carbon dioxide at the end of the test is measured.
7	EN 17556:2019 Plastics - Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in soil by measuring the oxygen demand in a respirometer or the amount of carbon dioxide evolved	This document specifies a method for determining the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in soil by measuring the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer or the amount of carbon dioxide evolved.
8	EN ISO 10210:2017 Plastics - Methods for the preparation of samples for biodegradation testing of plastic materials	This document describes methods for the preparation of test samples used in the determination of the ultimate aerobic and anaerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in an aqueous medium, soil, controlled compost or anaerobic digesting sludge
9	EN ISO 14851:2019 Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in an aqueous medium - Method by measuring the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer	This document specifies a method, by measuring the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer, for the determination of the degree of aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials, including those containing formulation additives.
10	EN ISO 14852:2018 Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in an aqueous medium - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	This document specifies a method, by measuring the amount of carbon dioxide evolved, for the determination of the degree of aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials, including those containing formulation additives.

Committee	Standard	Scope
11	EN ISO 14853:2017 Plastics - Determination of the ultimate anaerobic biodegradation of plastic materials in an aqueous system - Method by measurement of biogas production	This document specifies a method for the determination of the ultimate anaerobic biodegradability of plastics by anaerobic microorganisms.
12	EN ISO 14855-1:2012 Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide - Part 1: General method	This part of ISO 14855 specifies a method for the determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastics, based on organic compounds, under controlled composting conditions by measurement of the amount of carbon dioxide evolved and the degree of disintegration of the plastic at the end of the test.
13	EN ISO 14855-2:2018 Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide - Part 2: Gravimetric measurement of carbon dioxide evolved in a laboratory-scale test	This document specifies a method for determining the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions by gravimetric measurement of the amount of carbon dioxide evolved.
14	EN ISO 15985:2017 Plastics - Determination of the ultimate anaerobic biodegradation under high-solids anaerobic-digestion conditions - Method by analysis of released biogas	This document specifies a method for the evaluation of the ultimate anaerobic biodegradability of plastics based on organic compounds under high-solids anaerobic-digestion conditions by measurement of evolved biogas at the end of the test.
15	EN ISO 16929:2019 Plastics - Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials under defined composting conditions in a pilot-scale test	This document is used to determine the degree of disintegration of plastic materials in a pilot-scale aerobic composting test under defined conditions. It forms part of an overall scheme for the evaluation of the compostability of plastics as outlined in ISO 17088.

Committee	Standard	Scope
16	EN ISO 17422:2019 Plastics - Environmental aspects - General guidelines for their inclusion in standards	This document provides a structure for inclusion of environmental aspects in standards for plastics products. It proposes an approach which is directed at minimizing any adverse environmental impact without detracting from the primary purpose of ensuring adequate fitness for use of the products under consideration.
17	EN ISO 18830:2017 Plastics - Determination of aerobic biodegradation of non-floating plastic materials in a seawater/sandy sediment interface - Method by measuring the oxygen demand in closed respirometer	This document specifies a test method to determine the degree and rate of aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials when settled on marine sandy sediment at the interface between seawater and the seafloor, by measuring the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer.
18	EN ISO 19679:2020 Plastics - Determination of aerobic biodegradation of non-floating plastic materials in a seawater/sediment interface - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	This document specifies a test method to determine the degree and rate of aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials when settled on marine sandy sediment at the interface between seawater and the seafloor, by measuring the evolved carbon dioxide.
19	EN ISO 20200:2015 Plastics - Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials under simulated composting conditions in a laboratory-scale test (now under review)	This document specifies a method of determining the degree of disintegration of plastic materials when exposed to a laboratory-scale composting environment.
20	CEN ISO/TR 21960:2020 Plastics - Environmental aspects - State of knowledge and methodologies	This document summarizes current scientific literature on the occurrence of macroplastics and microplastics, in the environment and biota. It gives an overview of testing methods, including sampling from various environmental matrix, sample preparation and analysis. Further, chemical and physical testing methods for the identification and quantification of plastics are described.

	Committee	Standard	Scope
21	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	EN ISO 7827:2012 Water quality - Evaluation of the "ready", "ultimate" aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in an aqueous medium - Method by analysis of dissolved organic carbon (DOC)	This document specifies a method for the evaluation of the "ready" and "ultimate" biodegradability of organic compounds at a given range of concentrations by aerobic microorganisms.
22		EN ISO 9408:1999 Water quality - Evaluation of ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in aqueous medium by determination of oxygen demand in a closed respirometer	This document specifies a method, by determination of the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer, for the evaluation in aqueous medium of the ultimate biodegradability of organic compounds and waste waters at a given concentration by aerobic microorganisms.
23		EN ISO 9439:2000 Water quality - Evaluation of ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in aqueous medium - Carbon dioxide evolution test	This document specifies a method, by determination of carbon dioxide (CO ₂), for the evaluation in an aqueous medium of the ultimate biodegradability of organic compounds at a given concentration by aerobic microorganisms.
24		EN ISO 9887:1994 Water quality - Evaluation of the aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in an aqueous medium - Semi-continuous activated sludge method (SCAS)	This document specifies a method for the evaluation of the biodegradability ("ultimate" or "primary") of organic compounds.
25		EN ISO 9888:1999 Water quality - Evaluation of ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in aqueous medium - Static test (Zahn-Wellens method)	This document specifies a method for the evaluation in aqueous medium of the ultimate biodegradability and, as additional information, the primary biodegradability and the total elimination from water, of organic compounds at a given concentration by aerobic microorganisms.

Committee	Standard	Scope
26	EN ISO 10634: 2018 Water quality - Preparation and treatment of poorly water-soluble organic compounds for the subsequent evaluation of their biodegradability in an aqueous medium	This document specifies techniques for preparing poorly water-soluble organic compounds (i.e. liquid and solid compounds) with a solubility in water of less than approximately 100 mg/l and introducing them into test vessels for a subsequent biodegradability test in an aqueous medium using standard methods.
27	EN ISO 10707:1997 Water quality -- Evaluation in an aqueous medium of the 'ultimate' aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds -- Method by analysis of biochemical oxygen demand (closed bottle test)	This document specifies a method, by analysis of biochemical Oxygen demand, for the evaluation in an aqueous medium of the "ultimate" biodegradability of organic compounds at a given concentration by aerobic microorganisms.
28	EN ISO 11733:2004 Water quality - Determination of the elimination and biodegradability of organic compounds in an aqueous medium - Activated sludge simulation test	This document specifies a method for the determination of the elimination and the biodegradability of organic compounds by aerobic micro-organisms.
29	EN ISO 11734:1998 Water quality - Evaluation of the "ultimate" anaerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in digested sludge - Method by measurement of the biogas production	This document specifies a screening method for the evaluation of the biodegradability of organic compounds at a given concentration by anaerobic microorganisms.
30	EN ISO 14593:2005 Water quality - Evaluation of ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in aqueous medium - Method by analysis of inorganic carbon in sealed vessels (CO ₂ headspace test)	This document specifies a method, by analysis of inorganic carbon, for the evaluation in an aqueous medium of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic substances at a given concentration of microorganisms.

31	Committee	Standard	Scope
		EN 14996:2006 Water quality - Guidance on assuring the quality of biological and ecological assessments in the aquatic environment	This guidance standard defines activities appropriate for ensuring that the quality of ecological assessments in surface waters (including rivers, lakes, transitional and coastal waters and the open sea) and sediments meets specified requirements. This standard also covers hydromorphological aspects relevant to ecological assessment.
		CEN ISO/TR 15462:2006 Water quality — Selection of tests for biodegradability	This document gives an overview of biodegradation tests for the aquatic environment standardized by ISO and provides recommendations on their use.
	CEN/TC 261 Packaging	CEN/TR 13910:2010 Packaging - Report on criteria and methodologies for life cycle analysis of packaging	This Technical Report establishes a set of best practice guidelines for undertaking those aspects of life cycle assessment specific to packaging and distribution systems.
		EN 13432:2000 Packaging - Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation - Test scheme and evaluation criteria for the final acceptance of packaging	This European standard defines the technical specification for the compostability of bioplastics products. It contains requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation, and a test scheme and evaluation criteria for the final acceptance of packaging.
		EN 14045:2003 Packaging - Evaluation of the disintegration of packaging materials in practical oriented tests under defined composting conditions	This European Standard is used to evaluate the disintegration of packaging materials in a pilot-scale aerobic composting test under defined conditions.
		EN 14046:2003 Packaging - Evaluation of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of packaging materials under controlled composting conditions - Method by analysis of released carbon dioxide	This European Standard specifies a method for the evaluation of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of packaging materials based on organic compounds under controlled composting conditions by measurement of released carbon dioxide at the end of the test.

37	Committee	Standard	Scope
		EN 14047:2002 Packaging - Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of packaging materials in an aqueous medium - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	This standard specifies a method to evaluate the ultimate biodegradability of packaging materials and its constituents by measurement of CO ₂ evolution.
38		EN 14048:2002 Packaging - Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of packaging materials in an aqueous medium - Method by measuring the oxygen demand in a closed respirometer	This standard specifies a method to evaluate the ultimate biodegradability of packaging materials and its constituents by measurement of O ₂ -consumption.
39		EN 17427:2020 (Draft) Packaging - Requirements and test scheme for carrier bags suitable for treatment in well-managed home composting installations	This document specifies a testing scheme and requirements for the designation of carrier bags of any materials that are considered to be suitable for the incorporation into well-managed home composting installations run by householders for personal uses.
40		EN 17428:2020 (Draft) Packaging - Determination of the degree of disintegration under simulated home composting conditions	This document specifies two methods of determining the degree of disintegration of test materials when exposed to a well-managed home composting conditions.
41	CEN/TC 292 Characterization of waste	EN 14735:2005 Characterization of waste - Preparation of waste samples for ecotoxicity tests	This document describes the necessary steps to be performed before carrying out ecotoxicity tests on wastes. The purpose of this European Standard is to provide guidance on the taking of the sample, transport, storage of wastes and to define preparation, for the determination of ecotoxicological properties of wastes under the conditions specified in this European Standard by biological testing either as raw wastes or water extracts from wastes.

	Committee	Standard	Scope
42	CEN/BT/WG 209 Biobased products	CEN/TR 16208:2011 Biobased Products: Overview of standards	This Technical Report analyzes a set of standards, documents and other reports, related to bio-based products.
43	CEN/TC 411 Bio-based products	CEN/TR 16957:2016 Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase	This Technical Report provides guidance on how to compile an inventory for the end-of-life phase in LCA of bio-based products.
44		CEN/TR 17341:2019 Bio-based products - Examples of reporting on sustainability criteria	This document provides examples of business to business (B2B) reporting in accordance with EN 16751 Bio-based products – Sustainability criteria. This Technical Report also offers some additional guidance to EN 16751.
45		EN 16575:2014 Bio-based products - Vocabulary	This document defines general terms to be used in the field of bio-based products, including horizontal aspects relevant for bio-based product standards.
46		EN 16640:2017 & EN 16640/AC:2017 07 Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	This document specifies a method for the determination of the bio-based carbon content in products, based on the 14C content measurement.
47		EN 16751:2016 Bio-based products - Sustainability criteria	This document sets horizontal sustainability criteria applicable to the bio-based part of all bio-based products, excluding food, feed and energy, covering all three pillars of sustainability; environmental, social and economic aspects.
48		EN 16760:2015 Bio-based products - Life Cycle Assessment	This European Standard provides specific life cycle assessment (LCA) requirements and guidance for bio-based products, excluding food, feed and energy, based on EN ISO 14040 and EN ISO 14044.

	Committee	Standard	Scope
49		EN 16785-1:2015 Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 1: Determination of the bio-based content using the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis	This part of EN 16785 specifies a method of determining the bio-based content in products, based on the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis.
50		EN 16785-2:2018 Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 2: Determination of the bio-based content using the material balance method	This part of EN 16785 specifies a method of determining the bio-based content in products using the material balance applied to a representative product batch in a production unit.
51		EN 16848:2016 Bio-based products - Requirements for Business to Business communication of characteristics using a Data Sheet	This document specifies requirements for transparent and non-misleading business to business communication of characteristics of bio-based products by means of a specific Data Sheet.
52		EN 17351:2020 Bio-based products - Determination of the oxygen content using an elemental analyser	This document specifies a direct method for the determination of the total oxygen content in bio-based products using an elemental analyser.
53	CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices	EN ISO 11266:2020 (Draft) Soil quality - Guidance on laboratory testing for biodegradation of organic chemicals in soil under aerobic conditions	This document provides guidance on the selection and conduct of appropriate test methods for the determination of biodegradation of organic chemicals in aerobic soils.
54	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17477:2020 (Draft) Algae and algae products — Identification of the biomass of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes — Detection and identification with morphological and/or molecular methods	This document specifies a method for the detection and identification of microalgae, macroalgae (seaweed), cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes by using morphological methods and/or molecular methods.

Table 3. ISO standards on plastics biodegradation and ecotoxicity

	Committee	Standard	Scope
1	ISO/TC 38 Textiles	ISO/NP 5228 Textiles - Measurement of emission mass of fibre debris from textile products for microplastics detection — Domestic washing method	The method describes how to wash an end textile product using a domestic washing machine, collect the fibre debris discharged from the wastewater of the washing machine and measure the amount for each product.
2	ISO/TC 61 Plastics SC 14 Environmental aspects	ISO/NP 5148 (New Work Item Proposal) Plastics — Assessment of specific aerobic biodegradation rate of solid plastic materials	This document specifies a method to determine the specific biodegradation rate of solid, non-water soluble plastic materials.
3		ISO/NP 5430 (New Work Item Proposal) Plastics — Marine ecotoxicity testing scheme for biodegradable plastic materials — Test methods and requirements	This document specifies test methods and evaluation criteria by addressing potential ecotoxicological adverse effects on marine organisms.
4		ISO/NP 5425 (New Work Item Proposal) Specifications for use of poly (lactic acid) in specific 3D printing applications	This document specifies marking, technical requirement, test method, detection rule, label, packaging, transportation and storage of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) filament for use in specific 3D printing, e.g. Fused Deposition Modelling.
5		ISO/NP 5424 (New Work Item Proposal) Compostable drinking straws	This document specifies the terms and definitions, basic requirements, technical requirements, test methods, inspection rules, marking, packaging, transportation and storage of compostable drinking straws.
6		ISO/NP 5412 (New Work Item Proposal) Biodegradable plastic shopping bags for composting	This document specifies the terms and definitions, requirements, test methods, inspection rules and packaging, transportation and storage of biodegradable plastic shopping bags for composting.

Committee	Standard	Scope
7	ISO 13975:2019 Plastics — Determination of the ultimate anaerobic biodegradation of plastic materials in controlled slurry digestion systems — Method by measurement of biogas production	This document specifies a method of evaluating the ultimate anaerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in a controlled anaerobic slurry digestion system with a solids concentration not exceeding 15 %, which is often found for the treatment of sewage sludge, livestock faeces or garbage.
8	ISO 15270:2008 Plastics — Guidelines for the recovery and recycling of plastics waste	This document provides guidance for the development of standards and specifications covering plastics waste recovery, including recycling.
9	ISO 16620-1:2015 Plastics -- Biobased content -- Part 1: General principles	This part of ISO 16620 specifies the general principles and the calculation methods for determining the amount of biobased content in plastic products. These calculation methods are based on the carbon mass or mass of each constituent present in the plastic products.
10	ISO 16620-2:2019 Plastics -- Biobased content -- Part 2: Determination of biobased carbon content	This document specifies a calculation method for the determination of the biobased carbon content in monomers, polymers, and plastic materials and products, based on the 14C content measurement.
11	ISO 16620-3:2015 Plastics -- Biobased content -- Part 3: Determination of biobased synthetic polymer content	This part of ISO 16620 specifies the method of determining the amounts of biobased part in the biobased synthetic polymer in plastics products. This calculation method for biobased synthetic polymer content is based on the mass of biobased synthetic polymer in the plastics products.
12	ISO 16620-4:2016 Plastics -- Biobased content -- Part 4: Determination of biobased mass content	This document specifies a method of determining the biobased mass content in plastics products, based on the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis.

Committee	Standard	Scope
13	ISO 16620-5:2017 Plastics -- Biobased content -- Part 5: Declaration of biobased carbon content, biobased synthetic polymer content and biobased mass content	This document specifies the requirements for the declarations and labels of the biobased carbon content, the biobased synthetic polymer content and the biobased mass content in plastic products.
14	ISO/DIS 17088:2020 (Draft) Plastics - Organic recycling - Specifications for compostable plastics	This document specifies procedures and requirements for the identification and labelling of plastics, and products made from plastics, that are suitable for recovery through aerobic composting.
15	ISO 22403:2020 Plastics -- Assessment of the intrinsic biodegradability of materials exposed to marine inocula under mesophilic aerobic laboratory conditions -- Test methods and requirements	This document specifies test methods and criteria for showing intrinsic biodegradability in marine environments of virgin plastic materials and polymers without any preliminary environmental exposure or pre-treatment.
16	ISO 22404:2019 Plastics — Determination of the aerobic biodegradation of non-floating materials exposed to marine sediment — Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	This document specifies a laboratory test method to determine the degree and rate of aerobic biodegradation level of plastic materials.
17	ISO 22526-1:2020 Plastics -- Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics -- Part 1: General principles	This document specifies the general principles and the system boundaries for the carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastic products.
18	ISO 22526-2:2020 Plastics -- Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics -- Part 2: Material carbon footprint, amount (mass) of CO ₂ removed from the air and incorporated into polymer molecule	This document defines the material carbon footprint as the amount (mass) of CO ₂ removed from the air and incorporated into plastic, and specifies a determination method to quantify it.

Committee	Standard	Scope
19	ISO/FDIS 22526-3:2020 (Final Draft) Plastics -- Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics -- Part 3: Process carbon footprint, requirements and guidelines for quantification	This document specifies principles and requirements for the quantification and reporting of the Process Carbon Footprint of biobased plastics (see ISO/CD 22526-1), being a partial carbon footprint of a bioplastic product, based on ISO 14067 and consistent with the ISO standards on life cycle assessment (ISO 14040 and ISO 14044).
20	ISO/CD 22526-4:2020 (Committee Draft) Plastics — Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics — Part 4: Environmental (total) footprint (Life Cycle Assessment)	This document provides specific life cycle assessment (LCA) requirements and guidance for biobased plastics products.
21	ISO 22766:2020 Plastics -- Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials in marine habitats under real field conditions	This document specifies test methods for the determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials exposed to marine habitats under real field conditions.
22	ISO/CD 23517-1:2019 (Committee Draft) Plastics — Biodegradable mulch films for use in agriculture and horticulture — Part 1: Requirements and test methods regarding biodegradation, ecotoxicity and control of constituents	This document is a standard for biodegradable plastic materials used to produce mulch films or biodegradable mulch films ready to be used for mulch applications in agriculture and horticulture.
23	ISO/DIS 23832:2019 (Draft) Test method for determination of degradation rate and disintegration degree of plastic materials exposed to marine environmental matrices under laboratory conditions	This document specifies test methods for the measurement of the physical degradation of samples made with plastics materials when exposed to marine environmental matrices under aerobic conditions at laboratory scale.

Committee	Standard	Scope
24	ISO/CD TR 23891:2020 Plastics - Recycling - Necessity of standards	The overall objective for this report is to give a brief overview of the current situation, existing standards and short description of different recycling techniques. The aim is to identify the necessity of standards in the plastics recycling system and give direction for the adoption of regional standards and/or the development of new and existing standards.
25	ISO/DIS 23977-1:2020 (Draft) Plastics -- Determination of the aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials exposed to seawater -- Part 1: Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	This document specifies a laboratory test method for determining the degree and rate of the aerobic biodegradation level of plastic materials.
26	ISO/DIS 23977-2:2020 (Draft) Plastics -- Determination of the aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials exposed to seawater -- Part 2: Method by measuring the oxygen demand in closed respirometer	This proposal specifies a laboratory test method for determining the degree and rate of the aerobic biodegradation level of plastic materials.
27	ISO/CD 24187:2019 Principles for the development of standards for investigation procedures of plastics in environmental matrices and related materials	This document describes the key points to be observed in the analysis of plastics in various environmental matrices. This includes the use of certain materials as well as the classification of plastics with regard to sampling and sample preparation or the determination of representative sample quantities.
28	ISO/NP 24542:2019 (New Work Item Proposal) Method for analysing micro plastics in waters with very low contents of suspended solid	

Committee		Standard	Scope
29	ISO/TC 122 Packaging SC 4 Packaging and environment	ISO 18606:2013 Packaging and the environment - Organic recycling	This document specifies procedures and requirements for packaging that are suitable for organic recycling. Packaging is considered as recoverable by organic recycling only if all the individual components meet the requirements.
30	ISO/TC 147 Water quality SC 5 Biological methods	ISO 10708:1997 Water quality — Evaluation in an aqueous medium of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds — Determination of biochemical oxygen demand in a two-phase closed bottle test	This International Standard specifies a method for the evaluation of the ultimate biodegradability by aerobic microorganisms of organic compounds, in particular poorly water-soluble compounds, at a given concentration.
31		ISO 16221:2001 Water quality — Guidance for determination of biodegradability in the marine environment	This International Standard specifies five methods for determining the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of organic compounds in the marine environment by aerobic microorganisms in static aqueous test systems. Standard degradation methods developed for testing in fresh water are modified and adapted to marine conditions.

Table 4. ASTM D20 standards on plastics biodegradation

Standard		Scope
1	D3826-18 Standard Practice for Determining Degradation End Point in Degradable Polyethylene and Polypropylene Using a Tensile Test	This practice covers the determination of a degradation-end point (a brittle point) for degradable polyethylene/polypropylene films and sheeting less than 1.0 mm (0.04 in.) thick.
2	D5208-14 Standard Practice for Fluorescent Ultraviolet (UV) Exposure of Photodegradable Plastics	This practice is intended to induce property changes associated with conditions that might be experienced when the material is discarded as litter, including the effects of sunlight, moisture, and heat.
3	D5272-08(2013) Standard Practice for Outdoor Exposure Testing of Photodegradable Plastics	This practice requires characterization of the duration of exposure in terms of solar-ultraviolet radiation. Results from this test can be used to compare relative rates of degradation for materials exposed at the same time in the same location.
5	D5338-15 Standard Test Method for Determining Aerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials Under Controlled Composting Conditions, Incorporating Thermophilic Temperatures	This procedure has been developed to permit the determination of the rate and degree of aerobic biodegradability of plastic products when placed in a controlled composting process.
6	D5511-18 Standard Test Method for Determining Anaerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials Under High-Solids Anaerobic-Digestion Conditions	This procedure has been developed to permit the determination of the rate and degree of anaerobic biodegradability of plastic products when placed in a high-solids anaerobic digester for the production of digestate from municipal solid waste.
7	D5526-18 Standard Test Method for Determining Anaerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials Under Accelerated Landfill Conditions	This procedure has been developed to permit determination of the anaerobic biodegradability of plastic products when placed in biologically active environments simulating landfill conditions.
8	D5988-18 Standard Test Method for Determining Aerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials in Soil	This test method determines the degree of aerobic biodegradation by measuring evolved carbon dioxide as a function of time that the plastic is exposed to soil.

Standard		Scope
9	D6691-17 Standard Test Method for Determining Aerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials in the Marine Environment by a Defined Microbial Consortium or Natural Sea Water Inoculum	This test method has been developed to assess the rate and degree of aerobic biodegradation of plastics exposed to marine microorganisms.
10	D6954-18 Standard Guide for Exposing and Testing Plastics that Degrade in the Environment by a Combination of Oxidation and Biodegradation	This guide is a sequential assembly of extant but unconnected standard tests and practices for the oxidation and biodegradation of plastics, which will permit the comparison and ranking of the overall rate of environmental degradation of plastics that require thermal or photooxidation to initiate degradation.
11	D7444-18a Standard Practice for Heat and Humidity Aging of Oxidatively Degradable Plastics	This practice indicates how to test the oxidative degradation characteristics of plastics that degrade in the environment under atmospheric pressure and thermal and humidity simulations, only, in the absence of any selected disposal environment such as soil, landfill, or compost.
12	D7475-20 Standard Test Method for Determining the Aerobic Degradation and Anaerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials under Accelerated Bioreactor Landfill Conditions	This test method is used to determine the degree and rate of aerobic degradation (as indicated by loss of tensile strength, molecular weight, possibly resulting in disintegration and fragmentation) and anaerobic biodegradation of plastic materials in an accelerated aerobic-anaerobic bioreactor landfill test environment.
13	D7991 – 15 Standard Test Method for Determining Aerobic Biodegradation of Plastics Buried in Sandy Marine Sediment under Controlled Laboratory Conditions	This test method determines the biodegradation level of plastic materials exposed to laboratory conditions that simulate the environment found in the sandy tidal zone.
14	D6400 – 19 Standard Specification for Labeling of Plastics Designed to be Aerobically Composted in Municipal or Industrial Facilities	This specification covers plastics and products made from plastics that are designed to be composted in municipal and industrial aerobic composting facilities. The properties in this specification are those required to determine if plastics and products made from plastics will compost satisfactorily, including biodegrading at a rate comparable to known compostable materials.

Standard		Scope
15	D6868 – 19 Standard Specification for Labeling of End Items that Incorporate Plastics and Polymers as Coatings or Additives with Paper and Other Substrates Designed to be Aerobically Composted in Municipal or Industrial Facilities	This specification establishes the requirements for labelling of materials and products (including packaging), wherein a biodegradable plastic film or coating is attached (either through lamination or extrusion directly onto the paper) to compostable substrates and the entire product or package is designed to be composted in municipal and industrial aerobic composting facilities.
16	WK16000 New Practice for Practice for Heat Aging of Oxidatively Degradable Plastics: Pre-Conditioning for Plastics that Degrade in the Environment by a Combination of Oxidation and Biodegradation	This practice is a modification of D5510-94 and is intended to be complementary to D 6954-04, Standard Guide for Exposing and Testing Plastics that Degrade in the Environment by a Combination of Oxidation and Biodegradation. It is a practice that indicates how to test the oxidative degradation stage of such plastics under thermal and humidity simulations in selected disposal environments such as soil, landfill or compost.
17	WK17751 New Test Method for Determining Biodegradation of Plastic Materials in the Marine Environment by Open System Aquarium Incubations	This test method is used to determine the weight loss as a function of time of plastic film materials (including formulation additives), when incubated under changing, open, marine aquarium conditions, which is representative of aquatic environments near the coasts. The goal of this test is to obtain data that will predict real world experiences based the extent and rate of biodegradation data of the same materials obtained from the laboratory test ASTM D6691.
18	WK19580 New Test Method for Determining the Aerobic Degradation and Anaerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials under Accelerated Bioreactor Landfill Conditions	Modification of D5525.94 test method for Anaerobic Biodegradation of Plastic Materials in Landfills to include oxidative degradation of plastic materials prior to landfill conversion to anaerobic conditions.
19	WK34780 New Specification for Plastic Materials that Anaerobically Biodegrade in Landfills	The standard specification establishes the minimum requirements for characterizing plastics as anaerobically biodegradable in landfills with various moisture content.

Standard		Scope
20	<p>WK42833</p> <p>New Test Method for Determining Aerobic Biodegradation of Plastics Buried in Sandy Marine Sediment under Controlled Laboratory Conditions</p>	<p>This standard test method determines the biodegradation level of plastic materials exposed to laboratory conditions that simulate the environment found in the tidal zone.</p>
21	<p>WK45054</p> <p>New Practice for preparing samples for ecotoxicity testing after soil degradation</p>	<p>The standard Practice is applicable to plastic materials. This standard Practice is used to produce samples of soil where plastic specimens have been degraded. The soil samples can then be used for subsequent ecotoxicity testing.</p>
22	<p>WK46445</p> <p>Reinstatement of D7081 - 05 Standard Specification for Non-Floating Biodegradable Plastics in the Marine Environment (Withdrawn 2014)</p>	<p>This ballot is to reintroduce ASTM D-7081 with modifications based on the responses and feedback from ASTM members. This specification focuses on the criteria for biodegradation, disintegration and toxicity.</p>
23	<p>WK62355</p> <p>New Test Methods for Test methods to determine bioassimilation of biodegradable plastic materials</p>	<p>This specification provides laboratory test methods that can be used to determine whether a plastic product that is intrinsically bio-degradable or contains a pro-oxidant/pro-degradant additive is abiotically degradable and whether it is non-ecotoxic and capable of bio-assimilation. It applies only to aerobic conditions likely to be found in the environment.</p>

Table 5. Other relevant standardization deliverables

	Organization	Standard	Scope
1	AFNOR	NF T51-800:2015 Plastics - Specifications for plastics suitable for home composting	This document specifies procedures and requirements for plastic products that are suitable for home composting. Plastic products are considered as suitable for home composting only if all the individual components meet the requirements. The following four aspects are addressed: biodegradation, disintegration during composting, negative effects on the biological process and negative effects on the quality of the resulting compost, including the presence of high levels of regulated elements. This document forms the basis for the labelling of plastic products suitable for home composting.
2		NF U52-001:2005 Biodegradable materials for use in agriculture and horticulture - Mulching products - Requirements and test methods	This document specifies the requirements for characterizing mulch products made of biodegradable materials, webs, used in agriculture and horticulture. It also specifies the test methods for evaluating these requirements as well as the packaging requirements, identification and marking of mulch products. It defines the classification of mulch products according to their lifespan on the ground.
3	UNI	UNI 11355:2010 Plastic Items Biodegradable in Home Composting – Requirements and Test Methods	The standard defines the requirements that plastic products must meet to be disposed of by home composting (aerobic biodegradation at room temperature). The standard takes into consideration the biodegradable materials at room temperature according to the UNI 11183 standard and defines the criteria according to which the products made with these materials are compostable in domestic composting systems.
4	SPCR	SPCR 141 - Appendix 1:2010 Industrially compostable polymeric waste – Requirements and test methods	
5		SPCR 141 - Appendix 2:2010 Polymeric waste compostable in small scale (home) composts – Requirements and test methods	
6	Circular Plastics Alliance	Declaration of the Circular Plastics Alliance	The declaration promotes development, update or revision of design for recycling guidelines for all plastic products, shift to zero plastic waste to nature and zero landfilling of plastic waste, increase the uptake of recycled plastics up to at least 10 million tonnes, and development of a harmonised EU value chain voluntary system to monitor volumes of recycled plastics used in European products.

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Work Package Leader	Austrian Standards International			
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